

Review of Education for all-round Development Physical, Mental, Emotional and Spiritual through Holistic Education

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Abstract

If we want to do the Holistic development of children, we should carefully observe different aspects of their development i.e. Physical, Mental, Emotional and Spiritual. These aspects are the main aspects of child's all-round development. Education plays an important role in the Holistic development of a child. Education provides a platform through which a child may be able to develop his/her personality. As the term Physical development is concerned it related to the development of internal as well as external organs of the body. We know physical growth and development implies orderly changes in size, proportion and function from cradle to grave. The physical development of the child is rhythmic and not regular.

Mental development of the learner is very important for efficient learning and proper development of personality. A child is born in a home where he remains constantly in the company of his mother through his infancy. Traditionally, it is said that a mother is equal to hundred teachers. The impressions and experiences which a child has in the formative years leave permanent and indelible impressions on his mind. From the point of view of psychoanalysis, the early childhood experiences are very important for the future development of personality. Emotional, condition the human behavior, effect his achievements and social relations. Therefore, proper study of emotional growth and development is of vital importance to educational psychologists, teachers and parents. We know that emotions are present in every individual, at every stage, it differ from person to person, temporary in nature, quality of displacement, the product of perception etc. it is helpful for normal development i.e. positive part of emotions: Love, Affection, Like, Amusement, Attraction and Happiness, otherwise it is negative part of emotions: Fear, Jealousy, Anger, Hate, Tension and Anxiety.

Keywords Whole Child Development, Physical Development, Mental Development, Emotional Development, Spiritual Development, Holistic Education.

Introduction

Holistic education is related to human's all Learning and experiences which he gets through all life. It does not exist in a single, consistent form. It is best described as a group of beliefs, feelings, principles and general ideas that share a family resemblance. It is more than the education of the whole student and addresses the very broadest development of the whole person at the cognitive and affective levels. It emphasizes the education of the student beyond the confines of the classroom and moves the concept of a child-centered educational approach to a much more radical programme of education. Holistic education focuses on the fullest possible development of the person, encouraging individuals to become the very best or finest that they can be and enabling them to experience all they can achieve from life and reach their goals. These experiences or achievements can be rare, special and deeply meaningful experiences for the individual or could

represent a position, role or vocation that they perceive as unique or special and is an important goal in their life.

This could be described as the “vision” of holistic education. Holistic education nurtures the broad development of the students and focuses on their intellectual, emotional, social, physical, creative or intuitive, aesthetic and spiritual potentials. There is an emphasis on life experience and learning beyond the confines of the classroom and the formal educational environment towards education as growth, discovery and a broadening of horizons. It leads learners towards actively challenging and changing cultural values to meet human needs. Holistic education has the capacity to lead the students into new areas of thinking, to broaden their personal and critical thinking and develop an appreciation of the world around them, and to realize the importance that relationships have within all these considerations. Importantly, holistic education has the capacity to empower students to think differently, to think creatively and reflect on their own values. Undoubtedly, teachers would encourage their students to develop into well-educated, informed and participating members of society. This aim is accommodated within holistic education and offers teachers a framework within which to work. It also seeks to develop students actively beyond academic excellence alone.

As well as aim of holistic education concerned these are to prepare students for a perfect and productive life in which their skills and attributes are constantly challenged, developed and applied as part of their lifelong learning. It is an educational journey of personal discovery starting within formal education and then continuing throughout life. The learning and life experiences are belong to all people through whole life and individuals which they gain in different ways from the various situations and demands that they are presented with. It could be argued that this is the aim of any good educational system. This is not disputed but while there remains a predominant focus on the value of a knowledge-based educational system the advantages of holistic education will not be realized.

Objective of study

To study holistic education and impact on holistic development of children.

Review of Literature

Prof. (Dr.) Sunita Nambiyar, 2021: Balancing digital exposure is key. While media can enhance learning, it's essential to monitor and limit screen time to avoid negative mental health effects. Encouraging offline activities and social interactions can help maintain interpersonal skills and emotional well-being. Parents play a critical role in guiding this balance. Striking the right balance between digital exposure and traditional social interactions is crucial for children's development. Increased media use can impact mental health negatively, so it's essential to manage screen time and encourage face-to-face interactions. Parents should actively supervise and set limits to foster a healthy learning environment and support social skills development.

Josep Gallifa, 2019: The study on “Holonc Theory and Holistic Education” explores how holonic theory integrates physical, biological, and cultural dimensions into a unified model. It examines holistic consciousness through a phenomenological lens, defining holistic education as encompassing preservation, profundity, projective action, and span. This approach not only challenges traditional and postmodern perspectives but also offers a framework for contemporary discussions in holistic pedagogy, emphasizing a comprehensive and integrative approach to education.

Steph MacAskill, 2015: The study suggests that many students see value in integrating holistic education into the K-12 curriculum, as it could enhance their preparedness for university and their overall personal development. However, there are differing opinions on the role and relevance of such education, indicating a need for further discussion and possibly tailored approaches to integrating holistic principles in education. This analysis could be useful for educators and policymakers looking to refine educational strategies to better support student success both academically and personally.

Main Text

Physical Development with Holistic Education

Physical development affects many other areas of development and consequently, children are learning. This is because, as we have already seen in earlier units, development is interconnected. Where children's physical development is being promoted through a range of different opportunities and also encouraged by the

adult, children likely to benefit. Promoting children's physical development includes being aware of children who are not showing typical development. This is important too because, if a child has a development delay or medical condition which affects their physical development, other areas of learning are likely to be affected. This is one reason why, in the early months and years a child's life, there are many screening programmes designed to pick up on any areas of potential difficulty.

Mental Development with Holistic Education

The traditional linear structure of learning with listed and numbered notes has been expanded in recent years by the process of Mind Mapping. Mind maps are used to generate, visualize, structure, and classify ideas, and as an aid to studying and organizing information, solving problems, making decisions, and writing. The element of a given mind map are arranged intuitively according to the importance of the concepts, and are classified into groupings, branches, or areas, with the goal of representing semantic or other connections between portions of information. Mind maps may also aid recall of existing memories. In this way, as memory enhancement tricks, learning and note taking techniques, and subliminal techniques for the rapid absorption of information and it becomes clear that boundaries of mental learning are expanding all the time.

Emotional Development with Holistic Education

Emotional development is a huge area of holistic learning and no group can be fully functioning unless it makes room for the emotional level. Learning improves greatly when feelings are addressed and participants feel safe, accepted, encouraged and appreciated. Sharing encourages authenticity and deeper connection with both us and others. By expressing the shadow we can more fully embrace the light, become more whole, and develop greater compassion and empathy. Techniques of catharsis also need to be available to anyone engaged in holistic learning. Bashing cushions, yelling in sound proofed rooms, 'acting into' emotions, pushing, holding etc. can all be used.

There are many techniques, and disciplines like co-counseling have a particularly good repertoire. Specific learning standards in social emotional learning (SEL) abilities have been established for every grade from kindergarten through the last year of high school. In the early elementary years students should learn to recognize and accurately label their emotions and how they lead them to act. By the late elementary years lessons in empathy should make children able to identify the nonverbal clues to how someone else feel; in junior high they should be able to analyze what creates stress for them or what motivates their best performance. And in high school the SEL skills include listening and talking in ways that resolve conflicts instead of escalating them and negotiating for win-win solutions.

Spiritual Development with Holistic Education

In this regards, if individual spirituality is acknowledged as the leading edge of the holistic process, a spiritual practice becomes invaluable. Regular meditation, excursions into nature, singing, dancing, yoga, writing or parenting can all become a spiritual practice. These are practical methods of cultivating development of the higher self, and can be quite different to a religious practice that may depend on a belief system and strict rules. Whether we are performing a daily chore such as doing the dishes, or immersed in our favourite pastime or creative outlet, such as hiking in the hills or painting in the studio, we can bring present moment awareness, to connect with our inherent joy and enthusiasm for life, and 'lose ourselves' in the art of simply being. We all have our unique path to follow.

Spiritual practice is personal and yet can be shared in our way of being. The Findhorn Foundation is in many ways a modern day monastery where people can be in the world without withdrawing completely and live a life of service and commitment to spirit, based on the practice of inner listening. At the heart of all paths and traditions, there is a common ground and ancient truth. Spiritual practice serves to strip away the confusion and turn our attention inward. In this

way we can contemplate and transform our thoughts and actions, align with spirit and recognize our perfect imperfections, by embracing ourselves and each other together we create a more peaceful world

Conclusion

Holistic Education is the mean power of regarding overall development of individual person. Holistic education is a comprehensive and integrative approach that prepares individuals not just for academic success but for life itself. By addressing the physical, mental, emotional, and spiritual dimensions, holistic education equips students with the skills, values, and understanding needed to navigate the complexities of life. It cultivates well-rounded individuals who are capable of contributing positively to society, living with purpose, and achieving personal fulfillment. Ultimately, holistic education paves the way for the development of compassionate, thoughtful, and balanced individuals who are equipped to make meaningful contributions to the world.

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